

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1945	Elizabeth Brumfiel	1965	1976	2010	w	American archaeologist (gender, political economy, and the relationship between these areas of scholarship)	1945-2012
1945	Joan Bresnan	1966	1966	2011	w	American linguist	
1945	Thomas A. Wasow	1967	1972	2014		American linguist	
1945	Östen Dahl	1968	1970	2015		Swedish linguist	
1945	Ray Jackendoff	1968	1969	2016		American linguist	
1945	Saúl Sosnowski	1969	1970	2011		Argentinean Professor of Latin American Literature and Culture	
1945	Royal Skousen	1969	1972	2012		American linguist (language modeling)	
1945	Gerard Kilroy	1969	1971			Polish Honorary Visiting Professor of English	
1945	Nicholas Postgate	1969	No	2013		British academic and Assyriologist	
1945	Helen May Leach	1969	1976	2008	w	New Zealand academic specialising in food anthropology	
1945	Ward W. Briggs	1969	1974	2011		American classicist and historian of classical studies	
1945	Brian MacWhinney	1970	1974	2011		American Professor of Psychology and Modern Languages	
1945	Charles M. Rosenberg	1970	1974	2018		American Emeritus Professor of Art History	
1945	Csaba Pléh	1970	1970			Hungarian psychologist and linguist	
1945	Richard Taruskin	1970	1976	2014		American Professor of Music (musicologist, music historian, and critic theory of performance, Russian music, 15th-century music, 20th-century music, nationalism, the theory of modernism, and analysis)	
1945	Toril Swan	1970	1970	2002	w	Norwegian philologist	
1945	Joan Bybee	1970	1973	2005		American linguist	
1945	Mera Joan Flaumenhaft	1970	1970	2018	w	American academic and translator who taught at St. John's College, Annapolis MD	
1945	Norman Stillman	1970	1970	2015		American emeritus Schusterman-Josey Professor and emeritus Chair of Judaic History	
1945	Michel Zink	1970	1970			French writer, medievalist, philologist, and professor of French literature, particularly that of the Middle Ages	
1945	Vladimir Mikhaylovich Alpatov	1971	1971			Russian linguist	

1945 John Waiko	1971	1982	2005	Papua New Guinean historian, anthropologist, playwright and politician
1945 José Bengoa	1971	1971	2014	Chilean historian and anthropologist
1945 Jerald T. Milanich	1971	1971	2010	American anthropologist and archaeologist, specializing in Native American culture in Florida
1945 Ian Tattersall	1971	1971	2013	British-American paleoanthropologist and a curator emeritus with the American Museum of Natural History in New York City, New York
1945 Ezra B. W. Zubrow	1971	1971		American anthropologist
1945 Charles Arthur Willard	1972	1972	2012	American linguist (argumentation and rhetorical theorist)
1945 Malcolm Baker	1972	2003	2019	British Distinguished Professor Emeritus in art history
1945 Tej Bhatia	1972	1978	2005	British Professor of Linguistics and Director of South Asian Languages
1945 Vladimir Braginsky	1972	1972	2010	Russian-British Professor of Southeast Asian languages and culture at SOAS
1945 Catherine Browman	1972	1978	2008 w	American linguist and speech scientist
1945 Howard Lasnik	1972	1972	2019	American linguist
1945 Laurence R. Horn	1972	1972		American linguist
1945 Richard C. Steiner	1972	1974	2010	American Semitist and a scholar of Northwest Semitic languages, Jewish Studies, and Near Eastern texts
1945 Geoffrey Nunberg	1972	1972		American linguist, researcher and an adjunct professor at the UC Berkeley School of Information
1945 Elaine Tarone	1972	1972	2010 w	American professor of linguistics
1945 Bambi Schieffelin	1972	1979	w	American linguistic anthropologist (language socialization, language contact, language ideology, Haitian Creole, and missionization)
1945 Michael Silverstein	1972	1972	2014	American the Charles F. Grey Distinguished Service Professor of anthropology, linguistics, and psychology
1945 Guido Bastianini	1972		2007	Italian papyrologist and palaeographer
1945 Anne Salmond	1972	1972	2001 w	New Zealand anthropologist, environmentalist and writer
1945 Jane E. Buikstra	1972	1972	2012 w	American anthropologist and bioarchaeologist
1945 Paul Richards	1972	1977	2011	British professor of technology and agrarian development at Wageningen University

1945 Bernard Arcand	1972	1972	2006	French-Canadian anthropologist, author and communicator
1945 R. J. Tarrant	1972		2013	American classicist and Emeritus Pope Professor of Latin
1945 Jean Gascou	1972		2014	French scholar and papyrologist
1945 Rada Iveković	1972	1972	2012 w	Croatian professor, philosopher, Indologist, and feminist
1945 Geoff Pullum	1973	1976	2007	British-American linguist
1945 Jan Koster	1973	1978	2010	Dutch linguist
1945 John Pollini	1973	1978	2007	American professor of Art History and History
1945 Deborah Tannen	1973	1979	2013 w	American linguist (discourse analysis)
1945 Liv Bliksrud	1973	1973	2015 w	Norwegian philologist
1945 Johanna Nichols	1973	1973	2017 w	American linguist
1945 Judith Irvine	1973	1973	2016 w	American the Edward Sapir Collegiate Professor of Linguistic Anthropology
1945 Joan M. Tenenbaum	1973	1978	w	American linguist, anthropologist and artist specializing in metalsmithing and jewelry
1945 William J. Murnane	1973	1973	2000	American Egyptologist and author of a number of books and monographs on Ancient Egypt
1945 Andrew H. Plaks	1973	1973	2007	American sinologist (study of the vernacular fiction of the Ming and Qing dynasties)
1945 John W. Tait	1973		2010	British the Edwards Professor of Egyptology
1945 Robert Patterson Gordon	1973	1973	2012	British Regius Professor of Hebrew
1945 Christian Giordano	1973	1973	2015	Swiss anthropologist and sociologist
1945 Christiane Sourvinou-Inwood	1973	1973	2007 w	Greek scholar in the field of Ancient Greek religion and one of the most influential Hellenists
1945 Paul Drew	1974		w	British Professor of Language Linguistic Science
1945 Christopher I. Beckwith	1974	1977		American linguist (Asian languages, Tibetan language)
1945 Patricia Crone	1974	1974	2014 w	Danish-American author, Orientalist, and historian specializing in early Islamic history
1945 Leith Mullings	1974	1975	2014 w	American author, anthropologist and professor
1945 Carsten Niemitz	1974	1974	2010	German anatomist, ethologist, and human evolutionary biologist
1945 Norman Sauer	1974	1974	2013	American forensic anthropologist
1945 Michael H Long	1975		2011	American linguist

1945 Remko Scha	1975	1983	2010	Dutch computational linguist
1945 Vijay Mishra	1975	1981	2015	Australian Professor of English Literature
1945 Wendy Wassying Roworth	1975	1977	2009 w	American professor emerita of art history
1945 Mona Abul-Fadl	1975	1975	2006 w	British scholar of contemporary Western thought and women's studies
1945 Helen Fisher	1975	1975	w	American anthropologist, human behavior researcher, and self-help author
1945 Sylvia Yanagisako	1975	1975	2019 w	American the Edward Clark Crossett Professor of Humanistic Studies and Professor in the Department of Anthropology
1945 Mariza Corrêa	1975	1982	2000 w	Brazilian anthropologist and sociologist
1945 Alfred Gell	1975		1997	British social anthropologist whose most influential work concerned art, language, symbolism and ritual
1945 Brian Lang	1975	1975	2008	British Scottish social anthropologist who served as deputy chairman of the British Library
1945 Alain Testart	1975	1975	2009	French social anthropologist, emeritus research director at the Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS)
1945 Frances Lannon	1975	1975	2015 w	British Fellow and Tutor in Modern History
1945 Fred Donner	1975	1975	2011	American scholar of Islam and Professor of Near Eastern History
1945 Kenneth Hyltenstam	1976	1978	2010	Swedish professor of bilingual research and works
1945 Marcel Erdal	1976	1976	2012	Turkish linguist and Turkologist
1945 Шатин Юрий Васильевич	1976	1977		Russian literature critic and linguist (Russian literature, theory of literature, semiotics, rhetoric, poetics, discourse analysis)
1945 Ираида Яковлевна Селютина	1976	1980	w	Russian philologist (Тюркология, экспериментальная фонетика, сопоставительно)
1945 Leon Serafim	1976	1984	2010	American academic, Japanologist, linguistic historian
1945 Juan Pedro Laporte	1976	1976	2010	Guatemalan prominent archaeologist best known for his work on the ancient Maya civilization

1945	Kaori O'Connor	1976	2004	2011	American Hawaii Native social anthropologist and writer known for academic and non-fiction works that combine anthropology with history and archaeology, for studies of science and society, and for her work on material culture, commodities of empire, fashion and the anthropology of food	
1945	Nancy Sorkin Rabinowitz	1976	1976	w	American classical scholar, specialising in ancient Greek literature and intersectional feminism	
1945	Peter Hunt	1977	No	2013	British literature critic (Children's Literature)	
1945	Andrew Radford	1977	1977	2013	British linguist (syntax, generative grammar, child language acquisition)	
1945	Francisco L. Lisi Bereterbide	1977	1985	2016	Spanish Full Professor of Greek Philology (Ancient Philosophy, Plato, Aristotle, History of Platonism, Political Philosophy)	
1945	Viktor Zhivov	1977	1977	2013	Russian-American philologist, specializing on the history of Russian language.	
1945	Craig Melchert	1977	1977	1995	American linguist (Anatolian branch of Indo-European)	
1945	Richard Okada	1977	1977	2012	American Professor of Japanese	
1945	Theraphan Luangthongkum	1977	1977	2010	w	Thai linguist, specializing in phonetics, linguistic fieldwork, lexicography and minority languages of Southeast Asia
1945	Abdellah Hammoudi	1977	1977	2016	Moroccan anthropologist, ethnographer	
1945	Akpenpuun Dzurgb	1977	1984	2019	Nigerian professor of Religious Studies	
1945	Peter d'Agostino	1978	1998	2015	American professor of Film and Media Arts and director of the NewTechLab	
1945	Susan Bassnett	1978		2010	w	British translation theorist and scholar of comparative literature
1945	John Roxborough	1978	1978	2015	American Honorary Fellow, Department of Theology and Religion	
1945	Annette Kuhn	1978			w	British author, cultural historian, educator, researcher, editor and feminist
1945	Glenys Lloyd-Morgan	1978		1998	w	British classical archaeologist
1945	Rosemary Joy Hendry	1979	1979	2010	w	British social anthropologist
1945	Ross Hassig	1979	1980	2003	American historical anthropologist specializing in Mesoamerican studies, particularly the Aztec culture	

1945	Janetta Rebold Benton	1980	1980	2012 w	American art historian (humor in art and in iconography, fantastic fauna, and gargoyles)	
1945	Nader Jahangiri	1980	1980	2010	Iranian linguist	
1945	Nina Grønnum	1981	1981	2010 w	Danish phonetician	
1945	Anastasia M. Shkilnyk	1981	1985	2010 w	Ukrainian-Canadian anthropologist	1945-2014
1945	Tania Li	1982	1987	w	British Professor of Anthropology (social)	
1945	Tove Bull	1982		2012 w	Norwegian linguist	
1945	John Flowerdew	1985	1990	2016	British Professor of Applied Linguistics	
1945	Robert Barrett	1990	No	2007	American figurative painter, former Fresno Art Museum Director	
1946	Douglas H. Ubelaker	1968	1973	2008	American forensic anthropologist	
1946	Wolfgang Klein	1968	1970	2011	German linguist	
1946	Andrew Hill	1968	1975	2013	British palaeoanthropologist and palaeontologist	1946-2015
1946	Ronald Kaplan	1970	1975	2013	American computational linguist	
1946	Harald Haarmann	1970	1970		German linguist and cultural scientist	
1946	Howard Giles	1970	1971	2018	British-American sociolinguist and the professor of communication	
1946	Geoffrey Samuel	1970	1975	2014	British professor of religious studies (ethnographic studies of Tibetan and other Indic religions, investigating topics such as yoga, tantra, and the subtle body)	
1946	Ruth Shady	1970		2013 w	Peruvian anthropologist and archaeologist	
1946	William Leap	1970	1970	2018	American anthropologist and professor in the Women's, Gender and Sexuality Studies Program	
1946	D. Kimbrough Oller	1971	1971	2013	American scientist (evolution of language, child phonology, speech-language pathology, and to the fields of bilingualism and second-language acquisition)	
1946	Mark Steedman	1971	1972	2012	British computational linguist and cognitive scientist	
1946	Robert Hobbs	1971	1975	2014	American art historian and curator specializing in twentieth-century art	
1946	Carlos Gussenhoven	1971	1984	2014	Dutch professor of linguistics	
1946	Joseph Pivato	1971	1971	2015	Canadian writer and academic who first established the critical recognition of Italian-Canadian literature and changed perceptions of Canadian writing	
1946	Lionel Basney	1971		1999	American poet and professor of English	

1946	Raymond J. DeMallie	1971	1971	2017	American anthropologist whose work focuses on the cultural history of the peoples of the Northern Plains, particularly the Lakota
1946	Luc Brisson	1971	1971	2012	Canadian-French historian of philosophy and anthropologist of antiquity
1946	Marianne Mithun	1972	1974	2008 w	American linguist (American Indian languages and language typology)
1946	Clive Upton	1972	1977	2012	British linguist (English language, sociolinguistics, dialectology)
1946	Naomi Baron	1972	1972	2016 w	American linguist and professor of linguistics
1946	Stephen Owen	1972	1972	2018	American sinologist (Chinese literature, particularly Tang dynasty poetry and comparative poetics)
1946	Cheryl Rubenberg	1972	1979	2014 w	American writer and researcher specializing in the Middle East, formerly an associate professor in the Department of Political Science
1946	Helen Perlstein Pollard	1972	1972	2014 w	American academic ethnohistorian and archaeologist, known for her publications and research on pre-Columbian cultures in the west-central Mexico region
1946	Carolyn Fluehr-Lobban	1972	1973	2013 w	American anthropologist and Sudanist and a co-founder and past president of the Sudan Studies Association
1946	Jonathan Friedman	1972	1972	2017	American anthropologist
1946	Didier Coste	1973	1978	2014	French-Australian Professor Emeritus of Comparative Literature
1946	Joyce Hill Stoner	1973	1995	2009 w	American art conservator, art history educator, lyricist
1946	Nicoletta Misler	1973		2016 w	Italian Professor of Modern East European Art
1946	Stein Haugom Olsen	1973	1978	2010	Norwegian literary writer (Professor of British Literature)
1946	Ivan Haralampiev	1973	1973		Bulgarian linguist, mediaeval
1946	Rayna Rapp	1973	1973	2016 w	American professor and associate chair of anthropology at New York University, specializing in gender and health; the politics of reproduction; science, technology, and genetics; and disability in the United States and Europe
1946	Don Brenneis	1973	1973		American anthropologist

1946 Melvin Konner	1973	1973		American the Samuel Candler Dobbs Professor of Anthropology and of Neuroscience and Behavioral Biology at Emory University
1946 Page DuBois	1973	1973	2020 w	American professor of classics and comparative literature
1946 Alexander Stephan	1973	1973	2007	German-American specialist in German literature and area studies
1946 James Collins	1974	1980	2013	American linguist (comparative linguistics, lexicography and sociolinguistics Melayo-Polynesian languages)
1946 David G. Goodman	1974	1982	2011	American academic, author, editor and Japanologist
1946 John D. Smith	1974	1974	2007	British professor of sanskrit at Cambridge
1946 Jean Comaroff	1974	1974	2012 w	South African Professor of African and African American Studies and of Anthropology
1946 Anthony Cohen	1974 No		2003	British social anthropologist
1946 Philip L. Kohl	1974	1974		American professor of Anthropology at Wellesley College
1946 Nora England	1975	1975	2013 w	American linguist, mayanist
1946 Paul Voestermans	1975		2014	Dutch researcher in Cultural Psychology, Social Psychology, Cognitive Science and Cognitive Psychology
1946 Robert Bauer	1975	1982	2006	American linguist (syntax, phonology, Sino-Tibetan languages (especially Cantonese))
1946 Alan Prince	1975	1975	2015	American linguist (optimality theory, phonology)
1946 Jean Bernabé	1975 No		2017	French (Martinican) linguist and writer
1946 Diane Larsen-Freeman	1975	1975	2012 w	American Professor Emerita in Education and in Linguistics
1946 Deborah Dash Moore	1975	1975	2005 w	American director of the Frankel Center for Judaic Studies and a Frederick G.L. Huetwell Professor of History and Judaic Studies
1946 Marianne Gullestad	1975	1984	2008 w	Norwegian social anthropologist
1946 Jacques Legrand	1975		2013	French linguist and anthropologist
1946 Emilio Moran	1975	1975	2012	Cuban-American anthropologist, currently the John A. Hannah Distinguished Professor of Global Change Science at Michigan State University (MSU)

1946 Helena Wright	1976 No		2013 w	American curator of graphic arts at the National Museum of American History
1946 Höskuldur Thráinsson	1976	1979	2016	Icelandic Professor of Icelandic linguistics
1946 Susan Gass	1976	1979	2011 w	American linguist
1946 Igor Pomykalo	1976 No		2004	Croatian-Austrian professional musician (early music) and independent researcher
1946 Alice Carmichael Harris	1976	1976	w	American linguist
1946 Bonnie Webber	1976	1978	2016 w	American computational linguist
1946 John Baines	1976	1976	2013	British Egyptologist and academic
1946 Anna Curtenius Roosevelt	1976	1977	w	American Professor of Anthropology (human evolution and long-term human-environment interaction), the great-granddaughter of United States President Theodore Roosevelt
1946 Patricia Alice Shaw	1976	1976	2014 w	Canadian linguist specializing in phonology and known for her work on First Nations languages
1946 George E. Marcus	1976	1976	2013	American professor of anthropology at the University of California, Irvine who focuses on the anthropology of elites
1946 Lawrence Fine	1976	1976	2013	American Professor of Religion
1946 Mark Seidenberg	1977	1980	2013	American Vilas Research Professor and Donald O. Hebb Professor of Psychology (Cognition and Cognitive Neuroscience)
1946 Nedal Al Mousa	1977	1984		Jordanish Professor of English and Comparative Literature
1946 Charles Lindholm	1977	1979	2016	American the University Professor of Anthropology
1946 Tamar Frankiel	1978		2012 w	American Professor of Comparative Religion at the Academy for Jewish Religion
1946 Gershon Hundert	1978	1982		Canadian historian of Early Modern Polish Jewry and Leonor Segal Professor at McGill University
1946 John Sillince	1979	1979	2011	British professor of Organization Studies (discourse, rhetoric)
1946 Judith L. Klavans	1979	1980	2013 w	American linguist and computer scientist
1946 P. Steven Sangren	1979	1980	2018	American socio-cultural anthropologist of China and Taiwan, and is a leading expert in the study of Chinese religion

1946	Charlotte Roueché	1979		2016 w	British academic who specialises in the analysis of texts, inscribed or in manuscripts, from the Roman, Late Antique, and Byzantine periods	
1946	Marcienne Martin	1980	1995	2011 w	French Associate Researcher at the ORACLE Laboratory (Réunion Observatory of Arts, Civilizations and Literatures in their Environment)	
1946	Hanne Gram Simonsen	1980	1990	2014 w	Norwegian professor emerita in linguistics (clinical linguistics)	
1946	Jaklin Kornfilt	1980	1980	2010 w	American theoretical linguist	
1946	Галина Старовойтова	1980	1980	1998 w	Russian politician and ethnographer known for her work to protect ethnic minorities and promote democratic reforms in Russia	1946-1998
1946	Saïd Amir Arjomand	1980	1980		Iranian-American scholar and Distinguished Service Professor of Sociology	
1946	Gerd Lüdemann	1980		2011	German New Testament scholar and historian	
1946	María Cecilia Graña	1981	1981	2006 w	Argentinean Professor of Latinamerican Literatures	
1946	Arnold Lebeuf	1981	1990	2019	Polish Professor of Cultural anthropology, Archaeoastronomy and Cultural astronomy	
1946	Ásdís Egilsdóttir	1982	1982	2013 w	Icelandic Professor Emeritus of Icelandic Medieval Literature	
1946	Stjepan Damjanović	1982	1982	2017	Croatian linguist, philologist and paleoslavist	
1946	Tom Brass	1982	1982	2014	British academic who has written widely on peasant studies	
1946	Lynn Theresa Garafola	1982	1985	2016 w	American dance historian, linguist, critic, curator, lecturer, and educator	
1946	Nedal Al-Mousa	1984	1984	2008	Jordanian Professor of English and Comparative Literature	
1946	Tsvia Walden	1984	No	2010 w	Israeli psycholinguist	
1946	Jean-Yves Pollock	1985	1985		French linguist	
1946	David E. Johnson	1989	1991	2016	American linguist (Latin American philosophy, and Latin American narrative)	
1946	Isaiah Ndung'u Mwaniki	2001	2001		Kenyan Senior Lecturer of Linguistics & Languages	
1946	Martin Marcienne	2005	2016	w	French Associate Researcher at the ORACLE Laboratory (language science)	
1947	Janet Holmes	1969	1970	2018 w	New Zealand sociolinguist	

1947	Larry M. Hyman	1970	1972	2011	American linguist
1947	John Boswell	1970	1975	1994	American historian (issue of religion and homosexuality, specifically Christianity and homosexuality)
1947	Denis Blondin	1970	No	2009	Canadian anthropologist and writer
1947	Alan Boraas	1970	1983	2017	American professor of anthropology (into the culture, history, and archaeology of the peoples of the Cook Inlet area of Alaska, and in particular has worked closely with the Dena'ina people of the Kenai Peninsula)
1947	Bernard Comrie	1971	1972	2015 w	British linguist
1947	Elizabeth Bates	1971	1971	2012 w	American Professor of cognitive science (Psycholinguistics)
1947	J. Marshall Unger	1971	1975	2014	American linguist (emeritus professor of Japanese)
1947	Jens Allwood	1971	1976	2012	Swedish linguist
1947	Jesús Antonio Cid	1971	1991	2012	Spanish Professor of Spanish Literature (Digital Humanities, Literatura)
1947	William Beeman	1971	1976		American Professor of Anthropology; Theatre, Speech and Dance; and East Asian Studies
1947	Ruth Yeazell	1971	1971	w	American literary critic
1947	Ádám Nádasdy	1971	1977	2013	Hungarian linguist and poet
1947	Trevor Pateman	1972	1983	1997	British writer, philosopher
1947	Pamela Munro	1972	1974	2019 w	American linguist (Native American languages)
1947	Luca Serianni	1972		2017	Italian linguist and philologist
1947	Karla Jay	1972		2009 w	American distinguished professor emerita at Pace University, where she taught English and directed the women's and gender studies program (pioneer in the field of lesbian and gay studies)
1947	María Cátedra	1972	1984	2012 w	Spanish anthropologist
1947	Denis-Constant Martin	1972		2008	French scholar (Political sociology and Political anthropology, notably in Africa, and popular sociomusicology)
1947	Dawn Chatty	1972	1981	2015 w	American social anthropologist and academic, who specialises in the Middle East, nomadic pastoral tribes, and refugees

1947 Douglas Davies	1972	1980	2018	British Welsh theologian, anthropologist, and academic, specialising in the history, theology and sociology of death
1947 Pier Marco Bertinotto	1973	1982	2017	Italian linguist
1947 Roberta Michnick Golinkoff	1973	1975	w	American the Unidel H. Rodney Sharp Professor of Education, Psychological and Brain Sciences, and Linguistics and Cognitive Science
1947 Stephen C. Levinson	1973	1977	2014	British Linguistic Anthropology (culture, language and cognition)
1947 Timur Kocaoglu	1973	1982		Turkish Professor of history and languages
1947 Humayun Azad	1973	1974	2004	Bangladeshi poet, novelist, short-story writer, critic, researcher, linguist
1947 Rik Pinxten	1973	1976	2010	Belgian professor and researcher in cultural anthropology
1947 Alexandra Cornilescu	1974	1985	w	Romanian linguist
1947 André Helbo	1974	1978	2016	Belgian Professor of semiotics and emeritus chair of Performance Studies
1947 Geert Booij	1974	1977	2015	Dutch linguist
1947 Julie Van Camp	1974	1982	2014 w	American Professor Emerita of Philosophy Dance
1947 Len Gougeon	1974	1974	2012	American Distinguished Professor of American Literature
1947 Reginald Gibbons	1974	1974	2015	American poet, fiction writer, translator, literary critic, and Professor of English and Classics
1947 Roger Friedland	1974	1977	2011	American cultural and religious sociologist
1947 Scott A. Sullivan	1974	1978	2016	American Professor of Art History, Texas Christian University
1947 Ronald Carter	1974	1979	2017	British linguist (English, Russian, and German), comparative literature
1947 Nigel Vincent	1974		2007	British linguist
1947 Kay Warren	1974	1974	2014 w	American academic anthropologist, known for her extensive research and publications in cultural anthropology studies
1947 Robin Dunbar	1974	1974	2007	British anthropologist and evolutionary psychologist and a specialist in primate

1947	Chris Stringer	1974	1974	2009	British physical anthropologist noted for his work on human evolution
1947	Diana E. Forsythe	1974	1974	1997 w	American leading researcher in anthropology and a key figure in the field of science and technology studies
1947	John Miles Foley	1974	1974	2011	American scholar of comparative oral tradition, particularly medieval and Old English literature, Homer and Serbian epic
1947	Penny Cousineau-Levine	1974		w	Canadian photography theorist, curator, artist and professor
1947	Barbara Cassin	1974	1974	2012 w	French professor of philology
1947	J. N. K. Mugambi	1974	1983	2016	Kenyan Professor of Philosophy and Religious Studies
1947	Greville Corbett	1975	1976	2012	British Distinguished Professor of Linguistics (founder member of the Surrey Morphology Group)
1947	Peggy Kamuf	1975	1975	2016 w	American the Marion Frances Chevalier Professor of French and Comparative Literature
1947	Alojzije Jembrih	1975	1977		Croatian literary historian, linguist, philologist, slavist and expert of the Kajkavian literature
1947	John A. Hawkins	1975	1975	2008	American linguist (English grammar, psycholinguistics, language universals, linguistic typology and historical linguistics)
1947	Elissa L. Newport	1975	1975	2015 w	American Professor of Neurology and Director of the Center for Brain Plasticity and Recovery
1947	Michael Noonan	1975	1981	2009	American linguist (functional and typological linguistics)
1947	Caroline Moser	1975	1975	2012 w	British academic specializing in social policy and urban social anthropology
1947	Bruno Latour	1975	1975	2017	French philosopher, anthropologist and sociologist
1947	Ted Polhemus	1975	1975		American anthropologist, writer, and photographer who lives and works on England's south coast
1947	Arthur Ollman	1975	1975	2019	American photographer, author, curator, professor emeritus and founding director of The Museum of Photographic Arts, San Diego
1947	Holly Pittman	1975	1990	w	American Near Eastern art historian and archaeologist, and an expert in Near Eastern glyptic art

1947	Mario Andreotti	1975	1975	2012	Swiss Germanist
1947	Cyril Edwards	1975	1975	2017	British medievalist and translator
1947	Basil Hatim	1976	1982	2007	Iraqi-British translator, interpreter, linguist
1947	chibba chumya	1976	1978	2013	Polish historian of language
1947	Ciarunji Chesaina	1976	1988	2011 w	Kenyan Professor of Literature
1947	Dietmar Zaefferer	1976	1980	2012	German Linguist
1947	George Yule	1976	1981	2012 w	British linguist (different branches of linguistics)
1947	Joao Andrade Peres	1976	1987	2013	Portuguese linguist
1947	Salikoko Mufwene	1976	1979	2010	Democratic Republic of the Congo the Frank J. McLoraine Distinguished Service Professor of linguistics (perspectives on languages in contact, pidgins, creoles, language evolution, language change, and bilingualism)
1947	John Local	1976	1976	2009	British phonetician
1947	James Miller	1976	1976	2013	American Chair of Liberal Studies, writer (about Michel Foucault, philosophy as a way of life, social movements, popular culture, intellectual history, eighteenth century to the present; radical social theory and history of political philosophy)
1947	Alan Nussbaum	1976	1976		American linguist of the Indo-European languages and a classical philologist
1947	Joseph Buttigieg	1976	1976	2017	Maltese-American literary scholar and translator
1947	Suliman Bashear	1976	1976	1991	Israeli leading Druze Arab scholar and professor
1947	Tom Dillehay	1976	1976	2013	American the Rebecca Webb Wilson University Distinguished Professor of Anthropology, Religion, and Culture
1947	Diana Kleiner	1976	1976	w	American the Dunham Professor of History of Art and Classics at Yale University
1947	Geert Jan van Gelder	1977	1977	2012	Dutch literature critic (Literary criticism and history, African studies)
1947	Lydia White	1977	1980	2018 w	Canadian linguist and educator in the area of second language acquisition (SLA)
1947	Christine Obbo	1977	1977	w	Ugandan socio-cultural anthropologist
1947	Claudia Tate	1977	1977	2002 w	American (African) noted literary critic and professor of English and African American Studies
1947	Kees Versteegh	1977	1977	2011	Dutch linguist and Arabist

1947 John R. Lukacs	1977	1977	2009	American anthropologist
1947 Thomas R. Martin	1978	1978		American historian (Greco-Roman world)
1947 Hilda Judith Koopman	1978	1984	w	American linguist
1947 Beverly Mayne Kienzle	1978 No		2015 w	American the John H. Morison Professor of the Practice in Latin and Romance Languages
1947 Valentine Daniel	1978	1978	1998	Sri Lankan (Tamil) academic, anthropologist and author
1947 Roy Ellen	1978		2012 w	British Professor of Anthropology and Human Ecology with a particular interest in ethnobiology and the cultural transmission of ethnobiological knowledge
1947 Jay Miller	1978		2018	American anthropologist who is known for his wide-ranging fieldwork with and scholarship about different Native American groups, especially the Delaware (Lenape), Tsimshian, and Lushootseed Salish
1947 Gawdat Gabra	1978	1978	2007	Egyptian Coptologist
1947 Harry Falk	1978		2012	German Director of the Institute of Indian Philology and Art History
1947 Henry Indangasi	1979	1980	2003 w	Kenyan Professor of Literature
1947 Patricia Karetzky	1979		2009 w	American the Oskar Munsterberg Lecturer in Art History
1947 Carla Bazzanella	1979 No		2012 w	Italian linguist
1947 Carl Pollard	1979	1984	2014	American Professor of Linguistics
1947 Carolyn Sargent	1979	1979	2012 w	American medical anthropologist
1947 Berit Backer	1979 No		1993 w	Norwegian social anthropologist and ethnographer
1947 Leif Rantala	1979 No		2010	Finnish-Swedish linguist (Sami languages, cultures of history)
1947 Darrell A. Posey	1979	1979	2001	American anthropologist and biologist who vitalized the study of traditional knowledge of indigenous and folk populations in Brazil and other countries
1947 Haijo Westra	1979	1979	2011	Canadian Professor emeritus, Dept of Classics and Religion
1947 Hossein Farhady	1980	1980	2006	Iranian applied linguist with more than forty years of studying, teaching and researching in and out of Iran
1947 Jennifer Daryl Slack	1981	1981	2015 w	American Professor of Communication and Cultural Studies, Humanities

1947	Ron Burnett	1981	1981	2018	Canadian Professor of Cultural Studies	
1947	José María Salvador-González	1981	1981		Spanish art historian, philosopher, art critic	
1947	Sarah Rubidge	1982	2000	2013 w	British Formerly Professor of Choreography and New Media	
1947	Barbara Hochman	1982	1982	2009 w	Israeli professor in the Department of Foreign Literatures and Linguistics	
1947	Luis Eduardo Luna	1982	1989	2011	Colombian anthropologist and noted ayahuasca researcher	
1947	Miriam Shlesinger	1983	1990	2007 w	Israeli-American linguist and interpreter	1947-2012
1947	Alan Page Fiske	1985	1985	2014	American social anthropologist (Psychological anthropology, social theory, social relationships, social/moral emotions, methodology; Africa)	
1947	Gyde Hansen	1985	1985	2011 w	Danish Professor in Translation Studies	
1947	Alan Duane Eames	1986		2007	American writer and an anthropologist of beer , who was described as the "Indiana Jones of Beer"	1947-2007
1947	Marta Lamas	1989	2011	2017 w	Mexican anthropologist and political science professor	
1947	Brian Paltridge	1991	1994	2014	Australian Professor of TESOL (Teachers of English to Speakers of Other Languages)	
1947	Pam Hirsch	1992	1992	2017 w	British Lecturer in English Literature; & Film	
1947	Isaiah Mwaniki	2001	2001	2010	Kenyan Senior Lecturer of Linguistics & Languages	
1948	Olivia Harris	1967	1967	2009 w	British social anthropologist whose work focused on the study of the Bolivian highlands	1948-2009
1948	Jeffrey Elman	1969	1977		American psycholinguist and professor of cognitive science (neural networks)	1948-2018
1948	Martin Brauen	1969		2011	Swiss cultural anthropologist	
1948	Francisco Lafarga	1970	1973	2010	Spanish Professor Emeritus of French Literature	
1948	Jean-Marc Poinot	1970		2015	French Art historian and curator	
1948	Robert Boyd	1970	1975		American anthropologist, Professor of the School of Human Evolution and Social Change	
1948	Tim Ingold	1970	1970	2018	British social anthropologist	
1948	Michael Hoey	1970	1984		British linguist and Baines Professor of English Language	
1948	Guglielmo Cinque	1971	No	2008	Italian linguist	

1948	Linda Dalrymple Henderson	1971	1975	2015 w	American Professor of Art History
1948	Edwin S. Williams	1971	1974	2017	American linguist
1948	Gudrun Dahl	1971		2015	Swedish social anthropologist
1948	Henry I. Schvey	1972	1977	2016	American Professor of Drama and Comparative Literature
1948	Manuel Casado Velarde	1972	1976	2015	Spanish linguist
1948	Christian Lehmann	1973	1973	2010	German linguist
1948	Donna Jo Napoli	1973	1973	2015	American writer of children's and young adult fiction, as well as a prominent linguist
1948	James Paul Gee	1973	1975	2019	American researcher in psycholinguistics, discourse analysis, sociolinguistics, bilingual education, and literacy
1948	Mark Royden Winchell	1973	1978	2008	American biographer, essayist, historian and literary critic
1948	Dagmar C. G. Lorenz	1973	1973	2017 w	German-American scholar of German studies and comparative literature
1948	Loren Lerner	1974		w	Canadian professor of art history
1948	Jerzy Rubach	1974	1974	2014	Polish linguist (phonology, Polish language)
1948	Guillemette Andreu-Lanoë	1974	No	2010 w	French Egyptologist and archaeologist
1948	Joyce Marcus	1974	1974	w	American Latin American archaeologist and professor in the Department of Anthropology, College of Literature, Science, and the Arts
1948	Roger Cribb	1974		2007	Australian archaeologist and anthropologist who specialised in documenting and modelling spatial patterns and social organisation of nomadic peoples
1948	Walter Lee Williams	1974	1974	2013	American former professor of anthropology, history, and gender studies
1948	John Day	1974	1976	2013	British English Old Testament scholar
1948	Katherine K. Young	1974	1978	2015 w	Canadian religious studies professor at McGill University.
1948	Francine R. Masiello	1975	1975	2012 w	American Professor Emerita of Spanish and Compative Literature
1948	Joško Božanić	1975	1988		Croatian Professor of Croatian Language and Literature

1948	Russell Vandenbroucke	1975	1978	2012	American theatre director, Professor of Theatre Arts, Director of Peace Studies
1948	Sheldon Pollock	1975	1975	2011	American scholar of Sanskrit, the intellectual and literary history of India, and comparative intellectual history
1948	Nina Etkin	1975	1975	2009 w	American anthropologist and biologist (medical anthropology, ethnobiology, and ethnopharmacology)
1948	Yasmine Zaki Shahab	1975	1994		Indonesian anthropologist
1948	Mary Louise Pratt	1975	1975	2001 w	American the Silver Professor and Professor of Spanish and Portuguese Languages and Literatures
1948	Francesc Fontbona	1975	1987	2014	Spanish Catalan art historian, writer, exhibition curator and specialist in Romanticism, Catalan Modernism and Noucentisme Arts
1948	Imad-ad-Dean Ahmad	1975	1975		Palestinian-American scholar and the president of the Minaret of Freedom Institute
1948	Judith Maxwell	1976	1982	2015 w	American Linguistic Anthropologist (Linguistics, Mayan languages, discourse; Mesoamerica, Guatemala)
1948	Ivan Kalmar	1976		2010	Czech-Canadian Professor of Anthropology
1948	Setha Low	1976	1976		American former president of the American Anthropological Association, a professor in environmental psychology
1948	William L. Jungers	1976	1976		American anthropologist, Distinguished Teaching Professor and the Chair of the Department of Anatomical Sciences
1948	David Singleton	1977	1977	2013	British language educator
1948	Marc Okrand	1977	1977	2013	American linguist (Klingon language, Mutsun language)
1948	Harriet Bjerrum Nielsen	1977	1977	2017 w	Danish philologist and Professor of gender studies
1948	Barbara J. Grosz	1977	1977	2008 w	American computer scientist and Higgins Professor of Natural Sciences (natural language processing and multi-agent systems)
1948	Stephanie Wroth Jamison	1977		w	American linguist (historical linguist and Indo-Europeanist)
1948	Ilana Löwy	1977	1977	2010 w	Polish-French historian of biomedical sciences and a feminist

1948 Deborah Gewertz	1977	1977	2013 w	American anthropologist known for his concept of cultural consonance and work on cultural models especially in the context of medical anthropology
1948 J. G. W. Henderson	1977	1977	2013	British Professor of Classics at Cambridge University
1948 John Hartley	1978	1990		British Professor of Cultural Science
1948 Donna M. Brinton	1978 No		2006 w	American applied linguist, author, and global educational consultant on methods of second language teaching
1948 Annie Rialland	1978	1978	2018 w	French linguist, Director of Research emerita of the CNRS Laboratory of Phonetics and Phonology
1948 David Andreoff Evans	1978	1982		American scientist in the field of computational linguistics (natural language processing, and in ontology learning, medical informatics)
1948 Neal R. Norrick	1978	1978	2013	American linguist
1948 Elton L. Daniel	1978	1978	2011	American historian and Iranologist
1948 Susana Onega	1979	1979	2019 w	Spanish Professor of English Literature
1948 Anthony Aristar	1979	1984	2013	South African linguist, the founder of the LINGUIST List (web)
1948 Kirsten Hastrup	1979	1980	2016 w	Danish anthropologist and professor of anthropology (conjunction between the history and culture of both Iceland and Greenland)
1948 Roberta Smith	1979 No		2017 w	American co-chief art critic of The New York Times and a lecturer on contemporary art
1948 Pierre Lamaison	1979		2001	French anthropologist
1948 Stevan Davies	1979		2015	American Professor of Religious Studies
1948 Michael Theobald	1979	1979	2016	German Professor of New Testament in the Catholic Theological Faculty
1948 Daniel Gile	1981	1984	2010	French doctoral degrees in Japanese and in linguistics (former mathematician)
1948 Manuel Veiga	1981	2011		Cape Verdean writer and a linguist
1948 William Caplin	1981	1981	2007	American music theorist
1948 Peter Dorman	1982	1985	2015	American epigrapher, philologist, and Egyptologist

1948	Susan Waller	1983	1999	w	American Professor of Art History (French and British art in the later nineteenth century, representations of race in the modern era, and self-portraiture and the social construction of the artist)	
1948	Ellen Contini-Morava	1983	1983	2013 w	American anthropological linguist	
1948	Grant Evans	1983	1983	2008	Australian-Laotian anthropologist and historian notable for his works on Laos	1948-2014
1948	Alexis Sanderson	1983	No	2015	British indologist and Fellow of All Souls College	
1948	Wolfgang Sperlich	1984	1991	2013	New Zealand linguist, education activist and writer (biographer of Chomsky Noam)	
1948	John Pemberton	1986	1989	2013	American anthropologist and Board of Governors Distinguished Service Professor Emerita at Rutgers University	
1948	Brendan Callaghan	1986		2013	British psychologist of religion	
1948	Katia Buffetrille	1987	1996	2007 w	French ethnologist and tibetologist	
1948	Dorit Kedar	1989	1995	w	Israeli painter, Senior Lecturer of Zen-Buddhism and Creative Arts, "Hamidrasha" Faculty of arts	
1948	Marcela Lagarde	1990	2019	w	Mexican academic, author, researcher, anthropologist, feminist activist and politician	
1948	Varvara Belolyubskaya	1991	1997	w	Russian (Yakut) Even linguist and poet	
1948	Horacio Xaubet	1992	1992	2011	Uruguayan Professor of Language and Literature	
1948	Ron Geaves	1994	1994	2013	British professor of the comparative study of religion	
1948	Jim Kusch	1995	1995		American Professor Language, Literature & Translation Studies	
1948	Dr. Munira Al-Azraq	1998	1998	2008	Saudi Arabian Associate Professor, College of Arts (linguistics)	
1949	Arjun Appadurai	1969	1976		Indian-American socioculture anthropologist	
1949	Fanny Rubio	1971	1975	2009 w	Spanish professor, researcher, and writer, an expert in contemporary Spanish poetry	
1949	Joseph Tainter	1971	1975		American anthropologist and historian	
1949	Josep Maria Nadal i Ferreras	1971	1975	2012	Spanish Professor of History of Language	
1949	Nacéra Benseddik	1971		2009 w	Algerian historian, archaeologist and epigrapher	
1949	Beth Segal Wright	1972	1978	2014	American Art historian, educator	
1949	Stoichita Victor I.	1972	1989		Romanian art historian, writer	

1949 Victor Friedman	1972	1975	2015	American linguist
1949 Cynthia Beall	1972	1976	w	American physical anthropologist (research on people living in extremely high mountains became the frontier in understanding human evolution and high-altitude adaptation)
1949 Emilio Suarez de la Torre	1973	1976		Spanish Professor of Greek Philology (literatura griega, Greek literature, Ancient Greece, classical studies, Greek religion)
1949 Jeffrey Heath	1973	1976		American Professor of Historical Linguistics, Morphology, Arabic and Linguistic Anthropology
1949 Frans Plank	1974	1980	2014	German Linguist
1949 Ivan Sag	1974	1976	2013	American linguist and cognitive scientist
1949 Mark Aronoff	1974	1974		Canadian linguist
1949 Jaume Vallcorba Plana	1974	1978	2014	Spanish philologist and publisher
1949 Jaume Medina	1974	1976		Spanish (Catalan) philologist, latinist, writer, translator and poet
1949 John R. Rickford	1974	1979	2019	Guyanese academic and author
1949 Myra Shackley	1974	1988	2011 w	British Professor of Culture Resource Management and Head of the Centre for Tourism and Visitor Management at Nottingham Trent University
1949 Christopher Fuller	1974	1976	2014	Sri Lankan-British emeritus professor of anthropology
1949 Stephen D. Glazier	1974	1981	2016	American Research Anthropologist at the Human Relations Area Files
1949 David Barton	1975	1976	2019	British linguist
1949 Robert D. Borsley	1975	1979	2017	British linguist
1949 William Foley	1975	1976	2014	American linguist
1949 Philip Rubin	1975	1975	2015	American cognitive scientist, technologist, and science administrator (behavioral and cognitive science and neuroscience at a national level)
1949 Alan Entwistle	1975	1975	1996	British philologist (Hindi language)
1949 Anvita Abbi	1975	1975	2014 w	Indian linguist and scholar of minority languages
1949 Susan Goldin-Meadow	1975	1975	w	American the Beardsley Ruml Distinguished Service Professor in the Departments of Psychology, Comparative Human Development
1949 John A. Lucy	1975	1987	2016	American linguist and psychologist

1949	Gayle Rubin	1975	1994	w	American cultural anthropologist best known as an activist and theorist of sex and gender politics
1949	Ward Keeler	1975	1982		American anthropologist
1949	Richard Coates	1976	1977		British linguist
1949	Keren Rice	1976	1976	w	Canadian linguist
1949	Ellen Broselow	1976	1976	w	American experimental linguist (second language acquisition and phonology)
1949	David Dean Shulman	1976	1976	2016	Israeli Indologist, poet and peace activist, known for his work on the history of religion in South India, Indian poetics, Tamil Islam, Dravidian linguistics, and Carnatic music
1949	Katalin É. Kiss	1976	1979	w	Hungarian linguist
1949	Avidov Lipsker	1976	1976		Israeli professor of Hebrew Literature
1949	Willy Vande Walle	1976	1976	2016	Belgian academic, author, Japanologist and Sinologist
1949	James Chatters	1976	1982	2012	American social anthropologist and academic, who specialises in the Middle East, nomadic pastoral tribes, and refugees
1949	Loring Danforth	1976	1978		American professor of anthropology
1949	Gérard Raulet	1976	1981		French philosopher, Germanist, and translator, specializing primarily in the thought of Herbert Marcuse and Ernst Bloch
1949	Linda Meyer Williams	1976	1979	2015 w	American sociologist and criminologist
1949	Graham Furniss	1977	1977	2013	British Professor of African Language Literature
1949	Mark Johnson	1977	1977	2017	American the Knight Professor of Liberal Arts and Sciences (embodied philosophy, cognitive science and cognitive linguistics)
1949	Ramón Saldivar	1977	1977		Mexican-American author, teacher and researcher of cultural studies and Chicano literature
1949	Scott DeLancey	1977	1980		American linguist (Tibeto-Burman languages, linguistic typology, historical linguistics)
1949	Carol Fowler	1977	1977	2008 w	American experimental psychologist
1949	Michel-Rolph Trouillot	1977	1985	2012	Haitian academic and anthropologist
1949	Stephen Plog	1977	1977	2011	American anthropologist, writer, and photographer who lives and works on England's south coast
1949	Henry A Green	1977	1982	2014	American Professor of Religion

1949	Greg Urban	1978	1978	2011	American anthropologist	
1949	Paul V. Kroskrity	1978	1977	2018	American linguistic anthropologist	
1949	Gilbert Herdt	1978	1978	2017	American Emeritus Professor of Human Sexuality Studies and Anthropology and a Founder of the Department of Sexuality Studies and National Sexuality Resource Center at San Francisco State University	
1949	Stephen Juan	1978	1978	2009	American scientist, educator, journalist, author, and media personality	
1949	Helmut Glück	1978	1978	2015	German linguist	
1949	Simon Hornblower	1978	1978	2016	British English classicist and academic	
1949	Elisabet Engdahl	1979	1980	2014 w	Swedish linguist (first linguist to investigate parasitic gaps in detail)	
1949	Jeannie Bell	1979		w	Australian (Indigenous Australian) linguist (Aboriginal languages and linguistics)	
1949	Philip Lutgendorf	1979	1987	2018	American Indologist	
1949	Karin Barber	1979		2017 w	British cultural anthropologist and academic, who specialises in the Yoruba-speaking area of Nigeria	
1949	Hermann Korte	1979	1979	2010	German academic specialising in German literature, language and linguistics	
1949	Robert A. Leonard	1980	1982		American forensic linguist	
1949	Ronald P. Schaefer	1980	1990	2015	American academic and linguist	
1949	Patricia Smith Yaeger	1980	1980	2014 w	American academic and literary critic	1949-2014
1949	Frederique Apffel-Marglin	1980	1980	2011 w	French professor emerita of Anthropology	
1949	Anne Middleton Wagner	1980	1980	2010 w	British art historian	
1949	Alessandro Lami	1980		2015	Italian classical philologist	1949-2015
1949	Tessa Hofmann	1980	1982	2007 w	German scholar of Armenian studies and sociology	
1949	Funso Aiyejina	1981	1981	2014	Nigerian Professor of Literatures in English (poet, short story writer, playwright)	
1949	Syeda Ummehani Ashraf	1981	1981	2014 w	Indian senior Professor of Urdu	
1949	Craige Roberts	1981	1987	2015 w	American linguist	
1949	Anna Belfer-Cohen	1981	1986	2019 w	Israeli archaeologist and paleoanthropologist	
1949	W. H. Bellinger, Jr.	1981	1981	2016	American Professor of Religion	
1949	Miguel Ramos Corrada	1982	1983	2013	Spanish professor (expert in Asturian literature)	1949-2013

1949 Michael Sells	1982	1982		Serbian-American historian and scholar of religion who is the current Professor of Islamic History and Literature
1949 Rachida Triki	1983	1983	w	Tunisian philosopher, art historian, and art curator, currently full Professor of Philosophy at Tunis University specialized in Aesthetics
1949 Deepak Kannal	1983	1993	2009	Indian art historian, sculptor and a former professor at the Department of Art History and Aesthetics
1949 Ngô Văn Doanh	1984	1984	2014	Vietnamese archaeologist, social scientist and cultural researcher
1949 Richard Wilson	1985	1985	2016	American Professor of Art and Archaeology (leading authority on Japanese ceramics history and technique, as well as an active potter)
1949 Timothy Montler	1986	1986	2014	American academic and linguist
1949 Philippe Descola	1986		2019	French anthropologist noted for studies of the Achuar, one of several Jivaroan peoples, and for his contributions to anthropological theory
1949 Patrice Yengo	1986	1986		Congolese political anthropologist
1949 Guram Chikovani	1988	1988		Georgian Full Professor, Arabic Studies (Arabic Language and Literature)
1949 Gabriele Azzaro	1988	No	2016	Italian Professor of English Language and Linguistics
1949 Thias (ST) Kgatla	1988		2015	South African Emeritus Professor of Science of Religion and Missiology
1949 J Coleman	1989	1991	2015	British researcher in Phonetics Laboratory
1949 Margaret Anne Jolly	1989		w	Australian historical Anthropologist recognized as a world expert on gender in Oceania
1949 Sarah Robbins	1993	1993	2009 w	American the Lorraine Sherley Professor of Literature